

Master in Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Open-Domain Zero-Shot Audio Tagging: Evaluation via Semantic Embeddings

Tolga Yapici

Supervisor: Panagiota Anastasopoulou

Co-Supervisor: Frederic Font

July 2025

Contents

1 Introduction	1
1.1 Motivation	1
1.2 Key Concepts	2
1.2.1 Folksonomy	2
1.2.2 Co-occurrence Based Tag Recommendation	2
1.2.3 Zero-Shot Classification	3
1.2.4 Audio-Text Representation Models	3
1.2.5 LAION-CLAP	4
1.3 Objectives	4
1.4 Scope	4
2 Background	6
2.1 Freesound Tag Recommender (RankST)	6
2.1.1 Co-occurrence Based Tag Recommendation	6
2.1.2 Rank Aggregation and Adaptive Cutoff	7
2.1.3 Limitations	8
2.2 Contrastive Language-Audio Pretraining	8
2.2.1 CLAP Model Architecture	8
2.2.2 Models & Benchmarks	9
2.2.3 Prompt Design	10
2.2.4 Challenges in Folksonomy-Based Tagging	10
2.3 Semantic Evaluation of Tag Recommendations	11

2.3.1	Limitations of Exact Matching	11
2.3.2	Embedding-Based Semantic Evaluation with SBERT	12
2.3.3	Application to Audio Tagging	13
3	Methods	14
3.1	Dataset and Preprocessing	14
3.1.1	BSD10k Dataset	14
3.1.2	Dataset Preprocessing	15
3.1.3	Tag Vocabulary	16
3.2	LAION-CLAP Embeddings	16
3.2.1	Audio Embeddings	16
3.2.2	Tag Embeddings	17
3.3	Tag Recommendation Systems	17
3.3.1	RankST	17
3.3.2	Zero-Shot Baseline	18
3.3.3	Zero-Shot with DF Weighting	18
3.4	Evaluation Methodology	19
3.4.1	Evaluation Metrics	19
4	Results	21
4.1	Zero-Shot Performance	21
4.2	RankST Benchmark	23
4.3	Results Overview	26
5	Discussion	28
5.0.1	Zero-Shot Tagging Performance	28
5.0.2	Impact of Embedding-Based Semantic Evaluation	28
5.0.3	Tagset Quality and Noise	29
5.0.4	Ground Truth Limitations	29
5.0.5	System Performance Comparison	30

6 Conclusion	32
List of Figures	33
List of Tables	35
Bibliography	36
A First Appendix	39
B Second Appendix	40

Dedication

To my loving family, my dear friends, and the beautiful city of Barcelona.

Acknowledgement

I thank my supervisors, Penny and Frederic, for their support and sincerity, and my friends in the Master's program and the Music Technology Group who have supported my growth academically and beyond.

Abstract

This thesis investigates open-domain zero-shot audio tagging on the BSD10k dataset, a curated heterogeneous subset of Freesound, using Contrastive Language–Audio Pretraining (CLAP) audio embeddings. To reduce the impact of rare and noisy labels, we apply a document frequency (DF) weighting scheme, which leads to substantial performance gains. We further introduce a semantic evaluation approach based on SBERT text embeddings, which captures semantically valid tags missed by exact string matching. This yields notable gains across systems, with the largest improvements in the baseline model and consistent improvements for both the DF-weighted variant and Freesound’s supervised tag recommender used for comparison. Together, the tag weighting and semantic evaluation demonstrate performance improvements beyond standard metrics. While the results show clear advances, zero-shot tagging with CLAP remains limited by incomplete generalization to folksonomy labels and sparse annotation coverage. Nevertheless, this work highlights the potential of zero-shot approaches to enable consistent and standardized audio annotation directly from raw audio.

Keywords: audio tagging; zero-shot classification; audio representation; semantic similarity; recommendation systems; open-domain

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Open-domain audio repositories such as Freesound host large-scale collections of user-contributed sounds. Freesound currently contains over 670,000 audio recordings spanning environmental sounds, sound effects, and instrumental samples [1]. These collaborative platforms rely on user-contributed tags (folksonomies), which provide essential metadata for the retrieval, discovery, and description of audio content. This user-driven approach provides broad coverage, but introduces inconsistencies as tag descriptions often exhibit subjectivity, synonymy, spelling variants, typographical errors, and multilingual entries [2]. Additionally, tag scarcity has been a known challenge in free tagging, resulting in inadequate annotations that limit descriptive coverage. Tag recommendation systems are therefore critical to support adequate and consistent annotation, improving metadata quality and enabling effective retrieval and organization at scale.

Freesound's tag recommendation system, introduced in 2012 [2], suggests tags based on tag co-occurrence patterns. Given one or more user-provided seed tags, it retrieves candidate tags that frequently appeared alongside those inputs in past annotations. The effectiveness of this method depends on the quality of the input tags and the coverage of the folksonomy. Additionally, since this metadata-based

approach does not incorporate audio content analysis, it cannot generate tag suggestions directly from the audio signal or operate when no seed tags are provided.

With the recent development of audio-text representation models, a fundamentally different approach has become possible for tag recommendation. Models such as Contrastive Language-Audio Pretraining (CLAP), trained on large datasets of audio-text pairs, learn joint representations of audio and natural language in a shared embedding space [3]. This shared representation enables downstream applications such as text-to-audio retrieval and zero-shot audio classification without requiring task-specific training [4]. This zero-shot classification framework can be extended to tag recommendation, where multiple labels are predicted for each audio clip.

This raises the question of how effectively zero-shot models can perform tag recommendation on diverse audio content compared to co-occurrence-based approaches.

1.2 Key Concepts

1.2.1 Folksonomy

Folksonomy (folk + taxonomy [5]) is a user-driven classification system created through collaborative tagging, where users freely assign descriptive tags to online resources, forming a collective vocabulary. In the context of Freesound, the folksonomy comprises more than 30,000 unique tags [2] and is continuously growing (Figure 5).

1.2.2 Co-occurrence Based Tag Recommendation

A tagging approach that suggests new tags based on historical tag co-occurrence data. In the context of Freesound, given a set of input (seed) tags, the tag recommendation system retrieves candidate tags that frequently co-occur with the input and ranks them using aggregation methods [2].

Figure 1: Freesound Tag Recommendation Interface [6]

1.2.3 Zero-Shot Classification

Zero-shot classification is the task of assigning labels to inputs without task-specific training [3]. Unlike supervised systems, zero-shot models do not require fine-tuning on the target dataset. In audio classification, zero-shot models can predict labels for sound categories that were not seen during training. First introduced in vision by Contrastive Language-Image Pretraining (CLIP) [7], this approach has since been extended to audio [3][4], enabling classification from natural language class descriptions.

Figure 2: Zero-Shot Audio Classification Framework [8]

1.2.4 Audio-Text Representation Models

Audio-text representation models encode both modalities into a joint embedding space. Trained on audio-text pairs, such models enable cross-modal retrieval and

zero-shot audio classification by comparing similarity between audio and text embeddings, typically using cosine similarity [3][4].

1.2.5 LAION-CLAP

LAION-CLAP (Contrastive Language-Audio Pretraining) is an open-source audio-text representation model trained on over 630,000 audio-text pairs spanning diverse audio content. Its architecture (shown in Figure 4) uses separate encoders for audio and text, optimized via contrastive loss to produce aligned audio-text embeddings [4].

1.3 Objectives

This thesis aims to evaluate whether a zero-shot audio-text model can effectively recommend tags for heterogeneous audio content without supervised training on the target dataset. The specific objectives are:

- Benchmark the performance of LAION-CLAP for tag recommendation in a zero-shot setting on Freesound.
- Compare zero-shot predictions with Freesound’s co-occurrence-based predictions in tagging accuracy.
- Evaluate whether semantic similarity metrics (via SBERT) capture meaningful tags missed by exact string matching.

1.4 Scope

This thesis evaluates zero-shot audio tagging performance on a curated heterogeneous subset of Freesound (BSD10k), representing diverse general-purpose audio content. Evaluation focuses on methods incorporating tag weighting via document frequency and semantic evaluation through sentence embeddings. Performance is measured using precision, recall, and F1-score computed under both exact string matching

and semantic matching criteria. Evaluations are performed in a zero-shot setting without fine-tuning or retraining of underlying models.

Chapter 2

Background

2.1 Freesound Tag Recommender (RankST)

2.1.1 Co-occurrence Based Tag Recommendation

The RankST algorithm (Font et al. 2012) is the foundation of Freesound’s tag recommendation system. It estimates tag relevance from tag-tag co-occurrence statistics. Tag co-occurrence counts are used to compute the tag similarity matrix $S = DD^T$, where each element s_{ij} indicates the number of sounds in which tags t_i and t_j appear together [2]. Given a set of input tags, RankST retrieves a list of candidate tags, taking the top- N most similar tags to each input tag. For example, for an input tag *drums*, the system may suggest related tags such as *percussion* or *rhythm* if these frequently co-occur in the annotations. This approach relies on the principle that if two tags frequently co-occur, they are likely to describe related sound content.

2.1.3 Limitations

RankST relies entirely on tag metadata and is constrained by the user-generated folksonomy and its inconsistencies. Its recommendations are limited to previously seen tags, and the quality of the output is heavily dependent on the seed tags, making the system sensitive to subjective or inconsistent annotations.

In addition, noise in the folksonomy propagates into the recommendations. Spelling variations, user-specific tags, non-semantic terms, and misspellings often appear in the output providing no semantic utility. For instance, for the inputs *drum* and *percussion*, the recommendations are *drums*, *percussive*, *percs*, and username tokens such as *sandyrb* (a username tagged across many uploads), seen in Figure 1.

Further limitations of this system are the absence of audio content analysis and the seed requirement. As a result, this system cannot predict labels directly from the audio signal itself and cannot operate in a cold-start setting.

2.2 Contrastive Language-Audio Pretraining

2.2.1 CLAP Model Architecture

CLAP models are trained on large corpora of paired audio–text data, enabling them to learn joint audio–text representations by training separate encoders for each modality [3][4]. In LAION-CLAP architecture, the audio encoder (e.g., PANN or HTSAT) processes mel-spectrograms, while the text encoder (e.g., BERT or RoBERTa) embeds natural language [4] (Figure 4).

These embeddings are projected into a joint 512-dimensional latent space and optimized via contrastive learning, maximizing the similarity of semantically aligned audio-text pairs while minimizing it for unrelated pairs, a method adapted from CLIP [3][4][7]. With this framework these models are able to learn semantically aligned cross-modal representations making them suitable for downstream tasks such as text-to audio retrieval, zero-shot audio classification, supervised audio classifica-

tion, and enabling them to generalize well to unseen categories without fine-tuning [4].

This framework enables inference through cosine similarity between an audio embedding and a set of candidate text embeddings, enabling audio classification in zero-shot settings [4]. Zero-shot performance of CLAP models have been validated on benchmark datasets such as ESC-50, UrbanSound8K and VGGSound, where they perform competitively with supervised models in classification accuracy [3][4].

Figure 4: Contrastive Language-Audio Pretraining Architecture [8]

2.2.2 Models & Benchmarks

Several CLAP variants have been developed, each differing in model capacity, training data scale, and application domain. MS-CLAP is trained on 128k diverse audio-text pairs [3], while LAION-CLAP scales training to over 630k pairs [4].

On closed-domain benchmarks, MS-CLAP achieves 82.6% zero-shot classification

accuracy on ESC-50 and 73.2% on UrbanSound8K. LAION-CLAP demonstrates improved performance with 89.1% accuracy on ESC-50 and 73.2% on UrbanSound8K [3] [4].

LAION-CLAP’s larger training scale and data diversity suggest greater potential for generalization across diverse audio content. However, on VGGSound, a large open-domain dataset with over 310 sound classes, LAION-CLAP’s accuracy drops to 29.1%, highlighting the increased challenge of classification in open-domain settings [4].

Dataset	Domain	# Classes	CLAP(MS)	LAION-CLAP
ESC-50 [9]	Environmental	50	82.6%	89.1%
US8K [10]	Urban	10	73.2%	73.2%
VGGSound [11]	Open-domain	310+	N/A	29.1%

Table 1: Zero-shot classification accuracy of CLAP models on benchmark datasets

2.2.3 Prompt Design

LAION-CLAP is trained on audio–text pairs structured as natural language sentences, typically of the form *This is a sound of [label]* [4]. At inference time, the phrasing of candidate class tags significantly influences the model’s zero-shot classification accuracy. Prompts structured as natural language sentences (e.g., “This is a sound of a dog barking”) align more closely with the model’s training distribution, resulting in higher audio-text similarity scores and improved classification performance. The study by Olvera et al. (2024) demonstrates that prompting with complete sentences and detailed acoustic descriptions consistently outperforms using isolated labels [12]. This makes prompt formatting a critical design choice in zero-shot tagging and classification with CLAP-based systems.

2.2.4 Challenges in Folksonomy-Based Tagging

Unlike standardized class labels typical of benchmark datasets, folksonomies consist of user-generated tags that are often noisy, inconsistent, and semantically overlapping [2]. As discussed in the *Analysis of the Folksonomy of Freesound* [13], the

Freesound folksonomy is characterized by a continuously growing and largely uncontrolled vocabulary (Figure 5), where users label sounds without constraints leading to inconsistencies in describing audio content. In this setting, CLAP must score thousands of candidate tags with widely varying granularity and relevance, increasing the risk of inaccurate or irrelevant predictions. These conditions increase the complexity for adaptation of zero-shot models to heterogeneous vocabularies.

Figure 5: Number of new tags introduced every month to Freesound (2005-2012) [13]

2.3 Semantic Evaluation of Tag Recommendations

2.3.1 Limitations of Exact Matching

Conventional evaluation of classification systems relies on exact string matching, where a predicted class label must match the ground truth. This approach fails to account for semantic equivalence between lexically different tags, such as synonyms (e.g., birdsong vs. chirping), plural forms (e.g., drum vs. drums), or spelling variants (e.g., color vs. colour). This leads to an underestimation of system performance, particularly in tag recommendation tasks where the vocabulary is highly variable.

2.3.2 Embedding-Based Semantic Evaluation with SBERT

Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) is a language model that produces token-level contextual embeddings, based on the multi-layer bidirectional Transformer encoder introduced by Vaswani et al. (2017) [14][15]. Sentence-BERT (SBERT) adapts BERT with siamese and triplet network training to generate sentence-level embeddings that capture semantic similarity beyond token-level representations [16]. Building on this, embedding-based approaches have been adopted in tasks such as audio caption quality assessment, measuring semantic similarity between predicted and reference captions [17], effectively addressing challenges of lexical variability.

Figure 6: BERT Transformer encoder architecture based on Vaswani et al. 2017 [15][18]

Figure 7: SBERT siamese adaptation of BERT architecture [16]

Figure 8: Audio caption semantic similarity measurement framework [17]

2.3.3 Application to Audio Tagging

Despite its adoption in captioning, semantic similarity has been underexplored as an evaluation method for tag recommendation systems. In this work, SBERT embeddings are used to evaluate tag recommendations, which are often multi-word concepts. Cosine similarity between embeddings of predicted and reference tags measures semantic relevance, effectively addressing the lexical variability of folksonomy-based ground truth and capturing semantically relevant tags missed by exact string matching.

Chapter 3

Methods

3.1 Dataset and Preprocessing

3.1.1 BSD10k Dataset

BSD10k [19] is an open-source dataset containing 10,309 audio clips from Freesound.org, totaling 32.5 hours. It covers categories defined by the Broad Sound Taxonomy (Figure 9), including music, instruments, speech, sound effects, and soundscapes. Audio clips vary in content, quality, and duration, exhibiting the heterogenous characteristics of Freesound [20]. Audio files are provided in a standardized 16-bit, 44.1 kHz format, with a maximum duration of 30 seconds. Each clip includes pre-extracted 512-dimensional LAION-CLAP embeddings. Metadata includes unique sound identifiers and user-provided tags.

Figure 9: Audio clip diversity in BSD10k [20]

3.1.2 Dataset Preprocessing

BSD10k was filtered to exclude all clips used to build the RankST co-occurrence matrix. Clips with Freesound ID $\leq 207,648$ were removed. This cutoff corresponds to the highest ID included in the RankST co-occurrence matrix, which was last updated on 19 November 2013 per Freesound GitHub metadata [21]. This step reduced the dataset from 10,309 to 3,106 clips.

Tag-level filtering was applied to retain only labels present in RankST’s vocabulary of 7,712 tags. This preprocessing removed out-of-vocabulary tags, ensuring all labels were within RankST’s prediction scope.

Clips were subsequently filtered based on annotation density, retaining only those with 5-15 tags to ensure adequate ground-truth coverage while excluding clips with sparse or excessive annotations. The final filtered dataset comprises 1,528 clips with a mean annotation density of 8.34 tags per clip.

3.1.3 Tag Vocabulary

3.1.3.1 RankST Tag Vocabulary

RankST’s tag vocabulary, comprising 7,712 tags, was extracted from the Freesound GitHub repository, which hosts the implementation of the RankST tag recommendation system [21]. This vocabulary defines the system’s fixed prediction scope which cannot be expanded without rebuilding the co-occurrence matrix.

3.1.3.2 Zero-Shot Tag Vocabulary

For the LAION-CLAP based zero-shot tag recommendation system, the tag vocabulary was defined as

$$\text{Tagset}_{\text{CLAP}} = \text{Tagset}_{\text{RankST}} \cap \text{Tagset}_{\text{BSD10k}}$$

This intersection constrains CLAP’s predictions to tags present in the evaluation set, preventing out-of-vocabulary predictions. As the dataset inherits Freesound’s case sensitivity and hyphen-based word separation, tags were normalized by lowercasing to consolidate duplicate terms, and by replacing hyphens with spaces to segment multi-word tags. The resulting tag vocabulary comprises 1,870 unique tags.

Figure 10: Example of tag normalization and deduplication

3.2 LAION-CLAP Embeddings

3.2.1 Audio Embeddings

Audio embeddings were obtained from the pre-computed 512-dimensional LAION-CLAP embeddings included in the BSD10k dataset, with each embedding stored by

their Freesound ID.

3.2.2 Tag Embeddings

Following the prompt design technique described in Section 2.2.3, four full-sentence templates were created to ensure diverse semantic coverage. Using these templates, four sentences were produced for each tag (Figure 11). Text embeddings were extracted using LAION-CLAP’s RoBERTa-based text encoder to generate 512-dimensional embedding vectors.

```
{Tag}.  
The sound of {tag}.  
A recording of {tag}.  
An audio clip of {tag}.
```

Figure 11: Prompt templates for tag embeddings

3.3 Tag Recommendation Systems

3.3.1 RankST

3.3.1.1 System Configuration

The RankST tag recommendation system was deployed locally using the source code from the Freesound GitHub repository [21] in a Docker container. The tag recommendation source code was modified to bypass the adaptive cutoff function (see Section 2.1.2) and return exactly 10 recommendations.

3.3.1.2 Input–Ground Truth Split

Following Font et al. (2012) [2], input-ground truth pairs were created for each audio clip by randomly selecting three tags as input, with the remaining tags assigned as ground truth. This split satisfies the input requirement for RankST while maintaining sufficient ground-truth coverage. A total of 1,528 test cases were generated with an average of 5.34 ground truth tags per clip.

Freesound ID	418422
Title	female laugh over guitar.mp3
Input tags	ambient, female, laugh
Ground truth	voice, guitar, vocal
Total tags	6

Table 2: Example of an input-ground truth split

3.3.1.3 Recommendation Generation

For each test case, the RankST tag recommendation system was queried through its local HTTP endpoint with input tag subsets of size $k \in \{1, 2, 3\}$. Each query returned a ranked list of 10 candidate tags per audio clip for each k -value, enabling comparison of recommendation performance across different input sizes.

3.3.2 Zero-Shot Baseline

Audio and tag embeddings for each clip (as detailed in Section [2.2.3](#)) were loaded. Cosine similarity between each audio embedding and each tag embedding was computed. For each tag, the maximum cosine similarity among its sentence variants were taken. The top 10 unique tags with highest cosine similarity per audio clip were retrieved as tag recommendations.

3.3.3 Zero-Shot with DF Weighting

This variant extends the zero-shot baseline by incorporating normalized logarithmic document frequency (DF) weighting. The weighting function is defined as

$$W_{\text{DF}}(t) = (1 - \alpha) + \alpha \frac{\log(1 + \text{df}_t)}{\log(1 + N)}$$

where $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ is a tunable parameter, df_t is the document frequency of tag t , and N is the total number of audio clips in the corpus. The cosine similarity between the audio and tag embeddings is scaled by $W_{\text{DF}}(t)$ to down-weight rare or overly specific tags, which often correspond to noisy descriptors. Therefore, the weighted similarity score for tag t is computed as

$$W_{\text{DF}}(t) \cdot \cos(\text{embedding}_{\text{audio}}, \text{embedding}_{\text{tag}}).$$

ID: 376477

Opening old door in Spain

Tag	Cosine similarity	W_{DF}	Weighted score
shatter	0.1418	0.5449	0.0773
breaking	0.1264	0.5759	0.0728
break	0.1135	0.6309	0.0716
broken	0.1316	0.5198	0.0684
smash	0.1184	0.5705	0.0675

Figure 12: Example of DF-weighted tag recommendations.

3.4 Evaluation Methodology

3.4.1 Evaluation Metrics

3.4.1.1 Exact Matching

Performance is evaluated using standard information retrieval metrics computed per audio clip. A predicted tag is considered correct if it matches a ground-truth tag by exact string match. Precision@10 measures the proportion of correctly predicted tags within the top-10 recommendations:

$$P@10 = \frac{|T_{10} \cap T_{GT}|}{|T_{10}|}$$

where T_{10} represents the set of top-10 recommended tags, and T_{GT} denotes the set of ground-truth tags.

Recall@10 measures the proportion of ground-truth tags that are correctly predicted within the top-10 recommendations:

$$R@10 = \frac{|T_{10} \cap T_{GT}|}{|T_{GT}|}$$

F1-score computes the harmonic mean of Precision and Recall:

$$F1 = 2 \cdot \frac{P@10 \cdot R@10}{P@10 + R@10}$$

3.4.1.2 Semantic Matching

Semantic similarity is computed using the all-MiniLM-L6-v2 SBERT model to encode predicted and ground-truth tags into 384-dimensional vectors. For each predicted tag t_p , cosine similarity is calculated with all ground-truth tags t_{gt} :

$$\text{sim}(t_p, t_{gt}) = \cos(\text{embedding}_{t_p}, \text{embedding}_{t_{gt}})$$

where embedding_{t_p} and $\text{embedding}_{t_{gt}}$ denote SBERT embeddings. A predicted tag is a semantic match if

$$\max_{t_{gt} \in T_{GT}} \text{sim}(t_p, t_{gt}) \geq \tau$$

where τ is a threshold parameter. Performance is evaluated using Precision@10, Recall@10, and F1 metrics using semantic matches.

t_p	t_{gt}	Cos. sim.	Match ($\tau = 0.7$)
beat	beat	1.000	✓
drums	drum	0.867	✓
rhythmic	rhythm	0.863	✓
vocal	voice	0.824	✓
woman	female	0.799	✓
metallic	metal	0.884	✓
breaking	break	0.920	✓

Figure 13: Semantic matching example for predicted tags t_p against ground-truth tags t_{gt} , collected across multiple audio clips.

Chapter 4

Results

Performance is reported using Precision@10, Recall@10, and F1 metrics as detailed in Section 3.4.1, under both exact string matching (Section 3.4.1.1) and semantic matching (Section 3.4.1.2) conditions.

4.1 Zero-Shot Performance

4.1.0.1 Exact Matching

System	Precision@10	Recall@10	F1
ZS Baseline	0.0051 \pm 0.0240	0.0093 \pm 0.0497	0.0062 \pm 0.0292
ZS DF-Weighted ($\alpha = 0.7$)	0.0305 \pm 0.0738	0.0515 \pm 0.1248	0.0367 \pm 0.0876

Table 3: Zero-shot tagging performance of CLAP-based systems under exact matching conditions. Reported as mean \pm standard deviation across test clips.

4.1.0.2 Semantic Matching

System	Precision@10	Recall@10	F1
ZS Baseline	0.0130 ± 0.0467	0.0230 ± 0.0968	0.0157 ± 0.0570
ZS DF-Weighted ($\alpha = 0.7$)	0.0488 ± 0.1099	0.0837 ± 0.1891	0.0590 ± 0.1309

Table 4: Zero-shot tagging performance of CLAP-based systems under semantic matching conditions ($\tau = 0.7$). Reported as mean \pm standard deviation across test clips.

4.1.0.3 Performance Overview

Figure 14: F1 performance of Zero-Shot systems (exact and semantic matching)

Figure 15: Number of clips with ≥ 1 hit for Zero-Shot systems (exact and semantic matching)

4.2 RankST Benchmark

4.2.0.1 Exact Matching

System	Precision@10	Recall@10	F1
RankST ($k = 1$)	0.0808 ± 0.1285	0.1550 ± 0.2445	0.0997 ± 0.1513
RankST ($k = 2$)	0.1333 ± 0.1441	0.2703 ± 0.2875	0.1687 ± 0.1740
RankST ($k = 3$)	0.1774 ± 0.1598	0.3540 ± 0.3070	0.2236 ± 0.1890

Table 5: Tagging performance of RankST for $k \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ under exact matching conditions. Reported as mean \pm standard deviation across test clips.

4.2.0.2 Semantic Matching

System	Precision@10	Recall@10	F1
RankST ($k = 1$)	0.1127 ± 0.1609	0.2341 ± 0.3585	0.1444 ± 0.2056
RankST ($k = 2$)	0.1734 ± 0.1747	0.3594 ± 0.3756	0.2212 ± 0.2157
RankST ($k = 3$)	0.2181 ± 0.1826	0.4434 ± 0.3754	0.2765 ± 0.2197

Table 6: Tagging performance of RankST for $k \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ under semantic matching conditions ($\tau = 0.7$). Reported as mean \pm standard deviation across test clips.

4.2.0.3 Performance Overview

Figure 16: F1 performance of RankST ($k \in \{1, 2, 3\}$) (exact and semantic matching)

Figure 17: Number of clips with ≥ 1 hit for RankST ($k \in \{1, 2, 3\}$) (exact and semantic matching)

4.3 Results Overview

System	Exact Matching				Semantic Matching				$\Delta F1(\%)$	$\Delta Hits(\%)$
	P	R	F1	Hits	P	R	F1	Hits		
ZS Baseline	0.005	0.009	0.006	72	0.013	0.023	0.016	136	+166.7	+88.9
ZS DF	0.031	0.052	0.037	293	0.049	0.084	0.059	369	+59.5	+25.9
RankST ($k = 1$)	0.081	0.155	0.100	651	0.113	0.234	0.144	739	+44.0	+13.5
RankST ($k = 2$)	0.133	0.270	0.169	983	0.173	0.359	0.221	1053	+30.8	+7.1
RankST ($k = 3$)	0.177	0.354	0.224	1145	0.218	0.443	0.277	1200	+23.7	+4.8

Table 7: Performance across all systems. Reported values are mean Precision@10 (P), Recall@10 (R), F1 and clips with ≥ 1 correct hit (Hits). $\Delta F1(\%)$ and $\Delta Hits(\%)$ values are exact vs semantic.

Figure 18: F1 performance across all systems (exact and semantic matching)

Figure 19: Number of clips with ≥ 1 hit across all systems (exact and semantic matching)

Chapter 5

Discussion

5.0.1 Zero-Shot Tagging Performance

The baseline zero-shot system achieves an F1 score of 0.006 under exact matching, highlighting the inherent challenge of open-domain audio tagging without task-specific training. Implementing normalized logarithmic document frequency (DF) weighting (Section 3.3.3) yields a substantial relative improvement, increasing the F1 score to 0.037, a 516.7% increase over the baseline. This approach effectively down-weights rare tags, which often correspond to uninformative labels, attenuating noise and improving discriminative performance in zero-shot tagging.

5.0.2 Impact of Embedding-Based Semantic Evaluation

Zero-shot systems demonstrate substantial improvements under semantic evaluation compared to exact matching. The zero-shot baseline model achieves a 166.7% increase in F1 score and an 88.9% increase in clips with at least one correct prediction. The DF-weighted system similarly achieves proportional gains under semantic evaluation, with a 59.5% increase in F1 score and a 25.9% increase in clips with at least one correct prediction.

Comparing the zero-shot baseline under exact matching ($F1 = 0.006$) to the DF-weighted system under semantic matching ($F1 = 0.059$) reveals an 883% relative im-

provement in F1, demonstrating substantial gains in zero-shot performance through weighted tagging and semantic evaluation, which reveals latent performance missed by exact matching.

In addition, semantic evaluation captures latent performance for RankST (up to a 44% increase in F1) highlighting the broader potential of embedding-based evaluation in MIR tasks.

5.0.3 Tagset Quality and Noise

The zero-shot tag vocabulary, comprising 1,870 unique tags, provides broad semantic coverage for open-domain audio tagging. Compared to curated open-domain datasets such as FSD50K [22] (200 classes) and VGGSound [11] (310+ classes), the zero-shot vocabulary is substantially larger. However, the extensive tagset is not indicative of higher semantic utility; analysis reveals considerable variation in tag quality with a large fraction of the tagset comprising noise. These include overly specific and semantically uninformative tags, such as proper nouns, technical identifiers, subjective terms and fragments (Table 8). While DF weighting provides an immediate mechanism to attenuate noisy tags, it does not fully eliminate noise inherent to the folksonomy. This inflated vocabulary impairs CLAP generalization, compromising zero-shot tagging performance.

Proper nouns	barcelona, japan, nasa, sony, ableton
Technical	16bit, bpm, midi, mono, vst, h4n
Subjective	nice, bad, cool, yes, no
Fragments	a, el, la, c3, fm, xy

Table 8: Examples of noisy tags sampled from the zero-shot tag vocabulary

5.0.4 Ground Truth Limitations

Ground truth comprises user-generated annotations exhibiting inconsistent descriptive coverage and high sparsity. This limits evaluation, as the system may produce relevant predictions not covered by the ground truth (Figure 20). Semantic

evaluation captures partial latent performance; however relevant predictions not represented in the ground truth cannot be captured, resulting in potential underestimation of system performance.

ID: 376477

Opening old door in Spain

Ground Truth	Relevant Predictions (missed)
door, wood, wooden, field recording, creak, spain, open, handle	smash, hit, break, chop

ID: 386219

Steel - Drop to forge

Ground Truth	Relevant Predictions (missed)
metal, tools, one shot	percussion, mallet, pipe

ID: 378558

Asoada impact low tube.wav

Ground Truth	Relevant Predictions (missed)
low, impact, hit, metal	clang, snare, hammer

ID: 236679

M-h (whispered).aif

Ground Truth	Relevant Predictions (missed)
female, speech, alphabet, mumble, english, letters, voice	whisper

Figure 20: Examples of relevant predictions missed due to limited coverage in ground truth annotations.

5.0.5 System Performance Comparison

RankST outperforms the zero-shot systems across all metrics under exact and semantic matching conditions. RankST with three input tags ($k = 3$) achieves the highest F1 (0.224 exact, 0.277 semantic), while zero-shot with DF weighting achieves 0.037 and 0.059, respectively. The performance gap is narrower when only one input tag is available ($k = 1$, F1 0.100 exact, 0.144 semantic), with RankST still

outperforming zero-shot by a substantial margin. Higher k values improve RankST performance by providing richer semantic context. However, this highlights the user dependency intrinsic to the method. In contrast, zero-shot tagging enables autonomous inference directly from audio input. Within this framework, tag weighting, combined with semantic evaluation yields greater performance, demonstrating viable optimization strategies for zero-shot tagging.

Chapter 6

Conclusion

This work evaluated open-domain zero-shot audio tagging on BSD10k using LAION-CLAP embeddings. The baseline system achieves an F1 of 0.006 under exact matching, highlighting the inherent challenge of open-domain tagging with folksonomy-based vocabulary. Normalized logarithmic document frequency weighting reduces the influence of rare and noisy tags, yielding a 516.7% relative improvement in F1. Semantic embedding-based evaluation using SBERT enables a more robust assessment of system performance by capturing semantically valid tags missed by exact matching. This results in a 167% relative F1 improvement for the baseline zero-shot system, a 59% improvement for the DF-weighted system, and up to 44% for RankST. The combination of tag weighting and embedding-based semantic evaluation demonstrates an 883% relative improvement in F1 score for zero-shot audio tagging and reveals latent performance overlooked by exact matching. Despite improvements, overall zero-shot performance remains lower than RankST across all metrics. The performance gap reflects CLAP’s limited generalization to folksonomy-based labels and the high sparsity of ground truth annotations that may not cover all zero-shot predictions. While RankST demonstrates greater performance, its input tag dependency limits autonomy and introduces variability in annotation quality. Alternatively, zero-shot tagging enables autonomous inference directly from audio, offering a scalable approach that supports more consistent and standardized annotation.

List of Figures

1	Freesound Tag Recommendation Interface [6]	3
2	Zero-Shot Audio Classification Framework [8]	3
3	Visualization of Tag Similarity Matrix S [2]	7
4	Contrastive Language-Audio Pretraining Architecture [8]	9
5	Number of new tags introduced every month to Freesound (2005-	
	2012) [13]	11
6	BERT Transformer encoder architecture based on Vaswani et al. 2017	
	[15] [18]	12
7	SBERT siamese adaptation of BERT architecture [16]	13
8	Audio caption semantic similarity measurement framework [17]	13
9	Audio clip diversity in BSD10k [20]	15
10	Example of tag normalization and deduplication	16
11	Prompt templates for tag embeddings	17
12	Example of DF-weighted tag recommendations.	19
13	Semantic matching example for predicted tags t_p against ground-truth	
	tags t_{gt} , collected across multiple audio clips.	20
14	F1 performance of Zero-Shot systems (exact and semantic matching)	22
15	Number of clips with ≥ 1 hit for Zero-Shot systems (exact and se-	
	mantic matching)	23
16	F1 performance of RankST ($k \in \{1, 2, 3\}$) (exact and semantic match-	
	ing)	24
17	Number of clips with ≥ 1 hit for RankST ($k \in \{1, 2, 3\}$) (exact and	
	semantic matching)	25

18	F1 performance across all systems (exact and semantic matching)	26
19	Number of clips with ≥ 1 hit across all systems (exact and semantic matching)	27
20	Examples of relevant predictions missed due to limited coverage in ground truth annotations.	30

List of Tables

1	Zero-shot classification accuracy of CLAP models on benchmark datasets	10
2	Example of an input-ground truth split	18
3	Zero-shot tagging performance of CLAP-based systems under exact matching conditions. Reported as mean \pm standard deviation across test clips.	21
4	Zero-shot tagging performance of CLAP-based systems under semantic matching conditions ($\tau = 0.7$). Reported as mean \pm standard deviation across test clips.	22
5	Tagging performance of RankST for $k \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ under exact matching conditions. Reported as mean \pm standard deviation across test clips.	23
6	Tagging performance of RankST for $k \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ under semantic matching conditions ($\tau = 0.7$). Reported as mean \pm standard deviation across test clips.	24
7	Performance across all systems. Reported values are mean Precision@10 (P), Recall@10 (R), F1 and clips with ≥ 1 correct hit (Hits). $\Delta F1(\%)$ and $\Delta Hits(\%)$ values are exact vs semantic.	26
8	Examples of noisy tags sampled from the zero-shot tag vocabulary	29

Bibliography

- [1] 2024 in numbers | The Freesound Blog. URL <https://blog.freesound.org/?p=2141>.
- [2] Font Corbera, F., Serrà Julià, J. & Serra, X. Folksonomy-based tag recommendation for online audio clip sharing (2012). URL <http://hdl.handle.net/10230/22736>. Publisher: International Society for Music Information Retrieval (ISMIR).
- [3] Elizalde, B., Deshmukh, S., Ismail, M. A. & Wang, H. CLAP Learning Audio Concepts from Natural Language Supervision. In *ICASSP 2023 - 2023 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, 1–5 (2023). URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/10095889>. ISSN: 2379-190X.
- [4] Wu, Y. *et al.* Large-scale Contrastive Language-Audio Pretraining with Feature Fusion and Keyword-to-Caption Augmentation (2024). URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/2211.06687>. ArXiv:2211.06687 [cs].
- [5] Folksonomy :: vanderwal.net. URL <https://vanderwal.net/folksonomy.html>.
- [6] Freesound. URL <https://freesound.org/>.
- [7] Radford, A. *et al.* Learning Transferable Visual Models From Natural Language Supervision (2021). URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/2103.00020>. ArXiv:2103.00020 [cs].

- [8] LAION-AI/CLAP (2025). URL <https://github.com/LAION-AI/CLAP>.
Original-date: 2022-03-06T20:12:49Z.
- [9] Piczak, K. J. ESC: Dataset for Environmental Sound Classification. In *Proceedings of the 23rd ACM international conference on Multimedia*, 1015–1018 (ACM, Brisbane Australia, 2015). URL <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2733373.2806390>.
- [10] Salamon, J., Jacoby, C. & Bello, J. P. A Dataset and Taxonomy for Urban Sound Research. In *Proceedings of the 22nd ACM international conference on Multimedia*, 1041–1044 (ACM, Orlando Florida USA, 2014). URL <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2647868.2655045>.
- [11] Chen, H., Xie, W., Vedaldi, A. & Zisserman, A. VGGSound: A Large-scale Audio-Visual Dataset (2020). URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/2004.14368>.
ArXiv:2004.14368 [cs].
- [12] Olvera, M., Stamatiadis, P. & Essid, S. A sound description: Exploring prompt templates and class descriptions to enhance zero-shot audio classification (2024). URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/2409.13676>. ArXiv:2409.13676 [cs].
- [13] Font, F. & Serra, X. ANALYSIS OF THE FOLKSONOMY OF FREESOUND (2012).
- [14] Devlin, J., Chang, M.-W., Lee, K. & Toutanova, K. BERT: Pre-training of Deep Bidirectional Transformers for Language Understanding (2019). URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/1810.04805>. ArXiv:1810.04805 [cs].
- [15] Vaswani, A. *et al.* Attention Is All You Need (2023). URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/1706.03762>. ArXiv:1706.03762 [cs].
- [16] Reimers, N. & Gurevych, I. Sentence-BERT: Sentence Embeddings using Siamese BERT-Networks (2019). URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/1908.10084>.
ArXiv:1908.10084 [cs].

- [17] Mahfuz, R., Guo, Y. & Visser, E. Improving Audio Captioning Using Semantic Similarity Metrics (2023). URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/2210.16470>. ArXiv:2210.16470 [cs].
- [18] Smith, B. A Complete Guide to BERT with Code (2024). URL <https://towardsdatascience.com/a-complete-guide-to-bert-with-code-9f87602e4a11/>.
- [19] GitHub - allholy/BSD10k. URL <https://github.com/allholy/BSD10k>.
- [20] Anastasopoulou, P., Torrey, J., Serra, X. & Font, F. Heterogeneous sound classification with the Broad Sound Taxonomy and Dataset (2024). URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/2410.00980>. ArXiv:2410.00980 [cs] version: 1.
- [21] MTG/freesound (2025). URL <https://github.com/MTG/freesound>. Original-date: 2012-11-07T18:25:03Z.
- [22] Fonseca, E., Favory, X., Pons, J., Font, F. & Serra, X. FSD50K: An Open Dataset of Human-Labeled Sound Events (2022). URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/2010.00475>. ArXiv:2010.00475 [cs].